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GLOBALIZATION: IMPACT ON HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

Education is undergoing constant changes under the effects of globalization. The effects of globalization on education bring rapid developments in technology and communications are foreseeing changes within learning systems across the world as ideas, values and knowledge, changing the roles of students and teachers, and producing a shift in society from Industrialization towards an information-based society. It reflects the effect on culture and brings about a new form of cultural imperialism. The rise of new cultural imperialism is shaping children, the future citizens of the world into 'global citizens', intelligent people with a broad range of skills and knowledge to apply to a competitive, information based society. Globalization and technological advancements are delivering and increasing access to the world and subsequently subjects should reflect this global outlook.

The internationalization of higher education can be linked to various internal and external changes in the international system. Externally, there have been changes in the labour market, which have resulted in calls for more knowledge and skilled workers, and workers with deeper understandings of languages, cultures and business methods all over the world. Education is becoming more invaluable to individuals. In today's environment, education provides individuals with a better chance of employment, which in turn leads to a better lifestyle, power and status. The commodification of knowledge as intellectual property has occurred particularly with regard to connecting the intellectual work of universities with community, business, and government interests and priorities. While such a tendency is often welcomed by so-called applied disciplines, it causes tensions between the more profitable applied subjects of science and technology, and those of basic theoretical enquiry, particularly in arts and humanities. It also creates institutional winners and losers. This paper analyze the effect of globalization on

education and also discusses about the impact of globalization on higher education, regulations, culture, allocation of operation funds etc.

Introduction:

Globalization is a process, which has affected many areas of human life, one of those being education. In the twentieth century, many developing countries have experienced growth in the educational facilities available to them due to the entry of institutions from the West. Some believe that this process is an invaluable opportunity for the people of the developing countries to raise their skills and standards of education. Others fear that it is merely a modern version of cultural imperialism that will lead to the creation of a universal, ultimately Western society. One aspect of the globalization of education has been the creation of 'twinning projects' between one Western and one non-Western university (www.ssn.flinders.edu.au). Through Globalization of education, which is being knowledge transfer from the Western countries into developing countries, is intended to improve the skills and capabilities of the people receiving it.

Bull and Watson wrote in their book 'The Expansion of International Society' that the European elites who entered India were accused of Western imperialism actually rediscovered India's languages and religions and identified the region's social, legal and political traditions and they also argued that the transplantation of Western institutions into developing countries shapes the behavior of those involved and thus makes for greater similarity with the people in which the institutions first evolved.

In fact a study has shown that the process of transferring such institutions results in an increasing similarity of outlooks and values. David Orr (1999) argued that Western education has in fact replaced "indigenous forms of education throughout the world and focuses on preparing students exclusively for an urban existence." He also claimed that through this process, people are losing their vernacular knowledge, by which he meant 'the knowledge that people have of their places', that is a loss of their cultural worth and he also believed that "our graduates of tomorrow will be trained, above all, to keep the wheels of the global economy turning". But the Western style of education is inadequate as it focuses largely on the creation of money whilst paying no attention to the preserving of cultures.

Impact of Globalization in Higher Education:

Education is undergoing constant changes under the effects of globalization. The effects of Globalization on education bring rapid developments in technology and communications are foreseeing changes within school systems across the world as ideas, values and knowledge, changing the roles of students and teachers, and producing a shift in society from industrialization towards an information-based society. It reflects the effect on culture and brings about a new form of cultural imperialism. It brings rapid developments in technology and communications are foreseeing changes within school systems across the world as ideas, values and knowledge. The rise of a global society, driven by technology and communication developments are shaping children, the future citizens of the world into 'global citizens', intelligent people with a broad range of skills and knowledge to apply to a competitive, information based society. The future of countries often lies within their ability to compete in a global market where industrial based economies are giving way to knowledge based industries, realizing the importance of "knowledge, skills and the intellectual capacity to meet the challenges of accelerated change and uncertainty"

. Education is becoming a lifelong learning and training process, developing transferable skills and knowledge that can be applied to competitive markets where knowledge and information is being traded as a commodity.

The introduction of technology into the classroom is changing the nature of delivering education to students is gradually giving way to a new form of electronic literacy , more programs and education materials are made available in electronic form, teachers are preparing materials in electronic form; and students are generating papers, assignments and projects in electronic form". Video projection screens, books with storage device servers and CD ROMs as well as the emergence of on-line digital libraries are now replacing blackboards. Even exams and grades are gradually becoming available through electronic means and notebooks are starting to give way to laptops. Also, students can be examined through computer managed learning systems and do tutorial exercises on a computer rather than in a classroom. Such developments in education portray that there has been a shift from industrialization to information-based societies. Subsequently, technology is foreseeing a change in the education environment towards

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a reliance on electronic sources to deliver material. With such changes and the emergence of video conferencing and the Internet, the barriers of distance are being broken down at a rapid rate, due to the key aspect of globalization. Children and adults can now learn in a variety of ways and no longer have to be physically present in an education institution in order to learn, a definite advantage of flexible delivery systems. It allows for exploration of new areas of learning and thinking. The rapid growth of television services, with their immense influence as media of mass communication, has been very relevant in the technological shift. Other large contributions to this shift include the transistor and space satellites. Communication and information based technology over the years is the Internet, which is a massive network of computers located throughout the world.

These computers maintain libraries of text, images, computer software, and other forms of data that can be accessed by anyone, anywhere, at any time. This implementation of technology and communication to be successful and to educate a society, both the students and teachers need to be technologically literate. Communication technology is offering new challenges for students of all abilities as they can discuss issues of concern with their fellow students from around the world, thus developing communication and interpersonal skills, fostering a mutual understanding across countries and cultures. Developments in the delivery of education is allowing for individuals to explore new areas of learning and thinking that could not be done with pen and paper.

They are discovering knowledge through inquiry and experimentation rather than memorizing facts in a teacher dominated classroom setting. In fact, students no longer need to be physically present to learn as education material is becoming readily available over the Internet , through video conferencing, and tape recordings. Institutions are now turning towards the use of the Internet to deliver courses to students.

A shift in education is becoming evident where more responsibility is being placed on the individual for his or her learning, instead of solely on the teacher. Subsequently, the teachers themselves also need to be highly technologically literate, needing the competence and confidence to prepare students for a global information society.

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A global education should teach about issues that cross national boundaries, and interconnected systems on ecological, cultural, economical, political and technological grounds such as the Globalization program which draws upon expertise in many areas such as humanities, social science and environmental science. Globalization and technological advancements are delivering and increasing access to the world and subsequently subjects should reflect this global outlook just because of technology and communication seems to be creating in human life between the ‘haves’ and the ‘have not’s, resulting in a bifurcated society of those who can afford such information technology and those who can’t, so too does globalization (www.ssn.flinders.edu.au). While education institutions in western societies are embracing technology, developing countries are once again left behind, too weak and fragile to implement development programs for education, let alone introduce technology as well. While third world states encourage their citizens to seek more education, severe limitations in delivering basic services are a problem. A lack of infrastructure and funding makes it difficult to implement any technological and communication advancements.

However, despite differences in economy, political, culture and society, second and third worlds have adopted educational ideals from western thought and are anxious to appear modern and therefore promote education as a symbol of modernity and development to their own population and the foreign countries.

The spread of education internationally, as a result of globalization, has clearly had effects on cultures worldwide. The capitalist society is gradually becoming global with a strong emphasis on free trade emerging. Educational institutions have reacted accordingly, by becoming more market oriented, focusing their energy more on creating funds rather than providing sufficient education for students.

Due to this increasing free trade around the globe – to end protection in many sectors so that there is more competition and privatization, education is increasingly being drawn into this global capitalist competition. The Internationalization of education has become one of the key themes of educational policy and planning in the 1990s and the integration of worldwide capital and labour markets; educators are being forced to respond to a new set of challenges. The internationalization of education, particularly higher education, is a growing phenomenon.

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Universities and colleges around the world are increasingly becoming forced to compete in the global capitalist market and engage in entrepreneurial activity to sustain themselves in an increasingly 'uncertain world'.

The internationalization of higher education can be linked to various internal and external changes in the international system. Externally, there have been changes in the labour market, which have resulted in calls for more knowledge and skilled workers, and workers with deeper understandings of languages, cultures and business methods from all over the world. "Modern education...is almost exclusively focused on preparing children for an urban future,

The role of education has become more linked to globally competitive positions. Subsequent changes in university functions have lead universities toward "direct entrepreneurial activity to sustain themselves." This in turn produces a change in institutional approaches to the development of overseas education. University courses must now be cross-cultural in content, which is in association with the growing number of students, particularly in the 1990's, searching for higher education outside of their own country.

Education is becoming more invaluable to individuals. In today's environment, education provides individuals with a better chance of employment, which in turn leads to a better lifestyle, power and status.

Under the prevailing global forces, higher education institutions everywhere are subject to global trends. Universities now facing more challenges than ever before, the rise of a globalised knowledge-based economy has brought universities in many countries under closer scrutiny for the economic contributions they make. Governments have been particularly concerned that universities serve national interests in the global marketplace. There is an international tendency to emphasize the practical, technical value of higher education. The commodification of knowledge as intellectual property has occurred particularly with regard to connecting the intellectual work of universities with community, business, and government interests and priorities. While such a tendency is often welcomed by so-called applied disciplines, it causes tensions between the more profitable applied subjects of science and technology, and those of basic theoretical enquiry, particularly arts and humanities subjects. It also creates institutional winners and losers Under the impact of globalizing market forces, there

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has been a general trend towards the reduction of per capita public funding to higher education, at a time when the system is still expanding at both the initial and the 'life-long learning' levels. The burden of funding higher education is being shifted more and more to the shoulders of the individual on a 'users-pay' basis. Even public universities are increasingly funded by non-governmental sources, especially via student tuition and other fees, donations raised from alumni and others, and direct payment from business for services provided by the universities.

The linkage of performance to allocation of operation funds leads to intense competition among universities. Associated with that is the move to privatization of higher education. Tensions between academic and commercial based subject are increasing. Substantial decline in levels of public funding, the current globalization of higher education is mainly motivated by profits. Its goal is to meet market demand and to create a market for a variety of educational products. With substantial growth in the international student market, the issue of regulation of providers arises. It is extremely difficult to regulate the trade in academic institutions, programs, degrees or products across international borders. Lack of regulation is a major issue with the globalization of higher education.

They must engage with the issues of globalization, both theoretically as analysts and researchers, and practically as academic workers involved in an increasingly globalised enterprise. Universities providing a high quality education for the globalised world, despite its focus on internationalism and cross-cultural communication, are still based on an individualistic model of teaching. Education should not become a means of westernizing the world. On the contrary, it should treat each unique culture and society with due respect, realizing that global education is not only learning about the West, but also studying different cultures of the world, using different approaches, ways of teaching and different media. Another major problem with the global education system is accessibility. Many people in the developing world are still illiterate. According to a statistical analysis by UNESCO, literacy rates (percentage of people aged 15 and above who can read and write in their native language) in countries of Southern Asia in 1995 were as follows (www.uis.unesco.org):

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Country	Year	Both Sexes	Male	Female
Afghanistan	1995	32	47	15
Bangladesh	1995	38	49	26
Bhutan	1995	42	56	28
India	1995	52	66	38
Maldives	1995	93	93	93
Nepal	1995	28	41	14
Pakistan	1995	38	50	24
Sri lanka	1995	90	93	87

The table above, in five of the eight countries less than 50% of the population is literate and in six of them only less than 40% of women can read and writes. In the countries of sub-Saharan Africa the figures are even more disturbing, with only 14% of the population (21% male, 7% female) of Nigeria being literate, followed by 19% of the population (29% male, 9% female) of Burkina Faso (in 1995).

It is very surprise that today's global schooling system, supported by numerous international institutions (UNESCO being one of them), which has already achieved so much in the internationalization of pre-University and University education, is suffering a global crisis in the area of primary education.

Conclusion

Globalization has had many obvious effects on educational technology and communication systems change the way education is delivered as well as roles played by both teachers and students. The development of this technology is facilitating the transition from an industrial based society to an information-based one. At the same time, there is a dark side to globalization and to the very openness of the new information systems. While the richest countries grow richer, the poor are becoming poorer. Income, information and education gaps between the rich and the poor are widening not narrowing; economic crises, trade imbalances and structural adjustments have precipitated a moral crisis in many countries, tearing the basic social and cultural fabric of many families and communities apart, resulting in increasing youth unemployment, suicide, violence, racism and drug abuse and antisocial behavior from schools. .

In the 21st century, education systems face the dual challenge of equipping students with the new knowledge, skills and values needed to be competitive in a global market while at the same time producing graduates who are responsible adults, good citizens both of their country and of the world. Thus globalization challenges us to rethink not only how much education is needed but also its ultimate purposes.

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